

QUALITY MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATION IN HIGHER
EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEIs)

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Abstract. *This article talks about the conduct of education in higher education institutions, its quality and quality management. Quality management consists of such aspects as quality policy, purpose, responsibility, quality planning and management within the framework of the quality system leads to ensuring its improvement. Modern quality management in the management of educational processes means systematization of HEI activities, control, analysis of results, prospective strategic planning, taking into account every process affecting efficiency.*

Keywords. *Education, higher education system, higher education institutions, quality, policy, quality management, strategic planning.*

The development of globalization processes in the world sets the issue of training highly qualified, competitive personnel in line with the requirements of the labor market as a priority task. Today, in our country, the rapid development of economic sectors and the social sphere, the wide use of scientific-innovative potential with the full mobilization of scientific-intellectual and financial resources, and the modernization of scientific infrastructure to a new level in terms of quality are of great importance.

On the basis of modern educational trends, special attention is paid to the training of qualified personnel by reforming the higher education system and increasing its efficiency. One of the main problems is to create a scientific-based system of full formation of professional knowledge, skills and qualifications at the level of qualification requirements of branches and specialties.

In order to organize the educational process at a high level in the continuing education system, increase the effectiveness of education, and ensure consistency and continuity among the types of higher education, the qualification requirements and model training of professors, scientists, specialties it is important to effectively use the potential of experienced specialists of curriculum authors, employing enterprises, create a new generation of integrated educational literature, and implement modern pedagogical technologies in practice.

Integrating subjects - non-repetition of topics, saving time, that is, it allows to learn a large amount of material with less time, and it also represents the task of organization. It represents the reliance on existing knowledge, the use of the educational material in subsequent stages, the duration and integrity of the stages of the educational process.

The issue of the quality of education is now included among the important political processes in our country's strategy based on the priority principle "For human dignity". Explaining the concept of human value, the President said, "By human value, we mean the creation of decent living conditions and modern infrastructure for every citizen, providing qualified medical services, quality education, social protection system, and creating a healthy ecological environment. Special attention was paid to the improvement of the education system, which is one of the priority directions of the development of the social sphere, in the Action Strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, which is an integral continuation of the action strategy and includes 100 goals within the framework of 7 priority areas of development in the next 5 years, is to conduct a fair social policy, human capital in the direction of development, urgent tasks to improve the quality of education are defined.

Many researchers reject the complex and multi-dimensional nature of the concept of "quality of education", the abstract nature of the quality of education, and the content of the concept of high quality from the maximum correspondence to the tasks that must be solved during the training of a specialist for this level. It is emphasized that it consists of S.N. Severin and V.V. Savchuk came to the conclusion that the quality of education is an approach to modern social and technological requirements, developed on the basis of tools) emphasize that by setting goals, a certain opportunity is created to measure and define quality.

At the same time, relying on their personal views, the quality of education depends on the educational results of the level of subjects (teachers and students) - the level of the didactic process project - the level of opportunities (conditions and resources) created. and the need to consider five aspects such as subjective, conceptual, procedural, environmental and effective.

Different areas are cited by scientists as factors affecting the quality of education: the quality of management of the educational institution, the quality of personnel, the level of educational programs, the state of the educational process, the state of the infrastructure, the level of the educational environment, students' quality of engagement etc. No organization, enterprise or institution can achieve success without management.

In the management of higher education institutions, the efficiency of activity is seen in its management, the concepts of management and quality of education are the correct formation of trends in management of higher educational institutions based on a systematic and modern approach in all areas, the

development of a unique model of management and management functions, it is considered integral by defining the tasks of the subjects of the field.

The application of the principles of Total Quality Management (TQM) is important in the management of educational quality. Total quality management is a method that assumes that the results of the organization's intellectual activity can also be evaluated. Quality management consists of such aspects as quality policy, purpose, responsibility, quality planning and management within the framework of the quality system leads to ensuring its improvement. Modern quality management in the management of educational processes means systematization of HEI activities, control, analysis of results, prospective strategic planning, taking into account every process affecting efficiency. Taking into account that organizational processes are a set of structures, tasks, procedures and resources that provide management, its structural elements and their interrelationships, requirements and principles, functions, and quality indicators are determined.

The purpose of creating a quality system at HEIs is to improve the continuous education process and to achieve the quality of graduate training, as well as to increase the efficiency of using the existing potential of HEIs (personnel, research, resources).

The set goal requires solving the following tasks:

- ✓ determining the processes of educational activity of HEIs;
- ✓ identification of all processes;
- ✓ establishing mutual relations;
- ✓ coordinating the course of all organized processes, connecting them taking into account their intersection with each other;
- ✓ document description, registration and approval of all processes;
- ✓ implementation of documented processes and corrections if necessary.

One of the conceptual tasks of management is to create a motivational system focused on efficiency in a modern form while adhering to collective values

while developing the mission of HEIs. The use of operational (quick) management increases efficiency. Such a management approach involves providing a process in which tasks are quickly solved in a short period of time, which is encountered in the daily life of the university.

The effectiveness of the quality management system of the HEI depends on how it is modeled. perform inspections and self-assessments, serve for continuous improvement, corrective and preventive actions.

Currently, there are a number of models of quality management systems in universities in world experience:

- ❖ Quality management system model according to ISO 9001:2000 international standard;
- ❖ European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM) model and its modifications for higher education;
- ❖ Model of the Center for Higher Education Policy Research (CHEPS) of the University of Twente (Netherlands);
- ❖ Netherlands University Association model (VSNU);
- ❖ Belgium-Netherlands model (HBO Expert Group);
- ❖ Model of American National Quality Award "Baldrige National Quality Award" in the field of education;
- ❖ Standard (benchmark) test model for Australian universities.

Based on the above-mentioned theoretical and practical conclusions and proposals, the sources of demand and needs, which determine the tasks for the management of the quality of education in HEIs, can be expressed as follows.

The above creates the need to regularly launch internal monitoring studies, which will enable continuous development of relevant directions in HEIs, identify and analyze relevant indicators, and obtain the necessary information. Through this, it is possible to control and manage the level of influence of the factors that shape the final result of education.

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